

MJFF's Targets-to-Therapies (T2T) 2025 Program Summary

Validation Target Teams

- In 2025, we funded work to address key validation gaps for five priority targets. Expert co-chairs were recruited to help define these gaps, shape validation strategies, connect us with subject-matter experts, and support project selection. They will continue to guide these efforts throughout the project lifecycle to ensure strong scientific oversight
- The NOD2 target team is now fully funded and, over the next two years, will assess NOD2 genetic variants linked to PD risk or protection and their directional impact on PD biology; define the relationship between NOD2 and PD pathogenesis in patient samples and patient-derived cells; validate and test high-quality antagonist and agonist compounds, including GSK717, across structural and cellular assays; and evaluate the efficacy of NOD2-targeting small molecules in PD models. For more details on the NOD2 target team click [here](#).
- The Endolysosomal target teams will focus on key gaps in our understanding of TMEM175, MCOLN1, and ATP13A2, developing 1) pre-clinical models and mechanistic understanding to mimic human PD biology and capture the subtle effects of genetic risk variants (TMEM175, ATP13A2, and MCOLN1); (2) robust translational endpoints directly linking lysosomal ion channel/ATPase modulation to neuronal health (MCOLN1; TMEM175 and ATP13A2 planned); and (3) biological markers for detecting lysosomal dysfunction in human cohorts for use as potential target engagement and patient stratification strategies (TMEM175 initiated; TRPML1 and ATP13A2 planned).
- For OGA, we prioritized a multi-site collaborative effort to investigate the link between O-GlcNAc biology and PD patients. This project will directly address this key knowledge gap by quantifying total levels of O-GlcNAc, levels of a-syn and tau O-GlcNAc and a-syn site-specific O-GlcNAc modifications in PD patient brain tissue.
- Looking ahead to 2026, we plan to expand funding across priority targets spanning neuroinflammation, endolysosomal dysfunction, mitochondrial dysfunction, and protein aggregation pathways.
- Earlier this month, we hosted a Neuroinflammation Town Hall to launch a new funding call focused on STING1, TLR2, and TREM2. If you are interested in participating in these target-to-therapy efforts, please [complete a short survey](#) indicating how you would like to engage. To apply for funding, create a profile if you do not already have one and submit your application [here](#). The slides from the

townhall are available upon request.

Tools

- We have invested in tool development across our priority targets, including the generation and validation of antibodies, iPSC lines, and mouse models. These resources will be shared broadly with the research community.
- *Antibody development and validation:* YCharOS is performing knockout-validated testing of commercially available antibodies for T2T targets, with results to be published on Zenodo and F1000 by June 2026. Abcam is developing new antibodies and knockout cell lines for mouse and human NOD2, mouse USP30, mouse ATP13A3, and antibodies for human USP30, CACNA1D, and O-GlcNAc T72 aSyn. Immunoassay kits for O-GlcNAc T72 aSyn will also be produced.
- *iPSC Lines:* The Jackson Laboratory is generating iPSC lines for the endolysosomal targets TMEM175, TRPML1, and ATP13A2. These lines will be openly available, standardized, and accessible to both non-profit and for-profit groups .
- *Mouse models:* Three TMEM175 mouse models are being generated (TMEM KO, risk gene knock-ins and protective gene knock-ins) at Taconic.

Prioritization and Selection

- Over the past two quarters, we built a framework to prioritize symptomatic targets. We convened a multidisciplinary committee of clinical, industry, and academic experts to guide this effort. After identifying unmet patient needs across six key symptoms (Gait/Balance, Orthostatic Hypotension, Apathy, Executive Dysfunction, and Insomnia/EDS), we held a three-part workshop series with 40+ participants to systematically map critical gaps and evaluate potential strategies in both preclinical and clinical domains. We are now evaluating the most effective pathways to advance these opportunities in 2026, particularly those that fall outside T2T's core scope, and will align them with other MJFF programs where they can have the most significant impact.

Knowledge Base

- Our T2T Target Explorer is now live! The platform shares our target-prioritization approach, profiles of T2T priority targets, and details on funded projects for selected targets. We will continue to post updates as projects progress and share final results as they become available. [T2T Target Explorer knowledgebase](#)